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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Transnational Access to magnet testing facilities

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ABSTRACT

The transnational access MagNet fulfilled the engagements by giving 1932 access for 6 different projects. Unfortunately, GERSEMI due to delays in the infrastructure preparation and problems encountered in the user's side could not be operational.

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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1. Executive summary

WP9 (Magnet Testing)

The aim of the Trans-National Access (TNA) program is to offer a framework that facilitates sharing of the European research institute's complex infrastructures with researchers who, typically, are not part of the major projects and/or collaboration agreements in Europe or worldwide. This enables them to use these installations to perform novel experiments and tests. The Transnational Access (TA) within ARIES for magnet testing is set up at CERN and at University of Uppsala.

2. Description of infrastructure

2.1 MAGNET

The activity of the MagNet Transnational Access is within a Superconducting (Sc) Magnet Test Facility at CERN. This test facility composed by a high number of vertical cryostats and feed boxes, is essentially dedicated to the CERN projects and within those activities is allowing to perform Sc magnet test and qualifications. In general rules the vertical cryostats and the cryo cooler were the installations that were find the most adapted and requested by the users, which are indeed more adapted to the R&D work.

The test stands of the TNA are then composed by 5 vertical cryostats and 1 feed box for SC link. The magnet test benches are working at low temperature using liquid He at 1.9 or 4.2 K, while the superconducting link test stand requires cooling with He gas between 5-50 K. The installations were completed few years ago with a cryogen free cryostat allowing to test instruments up to 4.2 K. Powering capacities are up to 30 kA and magnets of large size: up to 4 m long and 600 mm diameter can be tested.

The test facility also borrowed in several occasion a magnet as part of the infrastructure to insure a background magnetic field for an experiment.

Finally, the installations are run by a well-trained team of experts in superconductivity and cryogenics allowing users to perform their test and make with the help of the team diagnostics and data interpretation.

2.2 GERSEMI

The FREIA Laboratory host the "Gersemi" versatile vertical cryostat test facility allowing to test Sc magnets and Sc RF cavities. Gersemi allows testing superconducting magnets and related equipment, located at Uppsala University, Sweden. It can be used for superconducting magnets with stored energy up to 350 kJ and is equipped with two power converters providing up to 2,000 A electric current.

This new test stand for magnets could not be fully operational from the beginning of the project and due to some delays of the potential users finally could not be used as TNA facility. On the other hand

the the facility get known by the community and will certainly be a successful and useful installation for SC magnet testing.

2.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE

WP9 has a common Selection Panel for both tasks 9.1 and 9.2. The entire panel has expertise in superconducting magnets. The selection panel is made of experts coming from 4 different worldwide laboratories: Tatsushi Nakamoto (KEK, Japan), Gianluca Sabbi (LBL, USA), and the two work package leaders Marta Bajko (CERN), Roger Ruber (Uppsala University).

Proposals are accepted at any time of the year. Within less than 2 weeks the adjudication was done. The selection criteria are mainly based on feasibility with the installations at MagNet and Gersemi and according to the test planning. In addition, we look after projects that can be combined with CERN program, scientific interest of the experiment, involvement of institutes or universities not being part of the community. Promotion of diversity, multiculturalism and multidisciplinary was considered an asset.

3. Summary of TA provided

The initial engagements of the TNA MagNet were 1900 access units and 8 projects, which was reviewed just after the COVID19 pandemic started, as this implied, as in many other institutes the limitation to access the infrastructures. The reviewed engagement (1300 access units) finally has been fulfilled and we could give even more than our initial engagement, as is reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Number of projects, users and access units for the MagNet testing facilities

Facility	No. of projects P3	Total P1+P2+P3	Total no. of projects Annex 1 (amended numbers)	No. of users P3	Total P1+P2+P3	Total no. of users Annex 1 (amended numbers)	No. of access units P3	Total P1+P2+P3	Total no. of access units Annex 1 (amended numbers)
MagNet	2	6	4	12	37	30	788	1932	1300
Gersemi	1	1	3	4	4	15	0	0	1,800

The Magnet being the active part of the TNA, could receive users from different countries in the graph below. We are proud of the fact that 14% of the users in the test facility were females.

4. Highlights of TA results

The first project we had in the test facility within ARIES was the so called: **SuShi** project led by *Dr. Barna*. Their project was to develop and demonstrate the feasibility of a superconducting shield (SuShi) for a septum. The test facility lend them a superconducting corrector magnets that they used for the experiment as part of the infrastructure. They spent 440 hours in the test facility and the measurements results have been reported in international conferences.

Dr. Varadnie with a team of students from a Hungarian University had the challenging project to develop an **automated measuring system for high voltage measurements** of superconducting magnets. They could us the facility and magnets to prove their system is working well in real operational conditions and profited also of the feed back of the experience of the test facility members. Finally, the students were also collaborating with the software team to improve the code associated to the instruments. They spent 288 hours in the facility.

Optical fibres as instrumentation to monitor the state of the superconductors ahs been done in SC transmission lines with a pervious TNA project (Eucard2). *Dr. Luca Palmieri* this time proposed to integrate fully **distributed fibres for monitoring temperature and strain at cold in a superconducting coil**. With his students he spent 192 hours in the facility and successfully completed with Leonardo Marcon his Phd using data of the measurements. Results were also published in international conferences both dedicated to optical fibres and SC magnets. For the very first time a high temperature superconducting coil has been monitored during it powering and the results showed the mechanical deformation of the whole winding before its transition to normal conducting state.

Dr. Giordano and his team, a user of the facility, cam this time to test in the cryo cooled different **materials that would allow him to make sensitive the fibres even at low temperature** and use them and instruments to monitor temperature and / or strain. He spent 24 h in the facility and published his results in conferences of optical fibres ([27th International Conference on Optical Fiber Sensors](#) .) and material science (IOP Conference Series Materials Science and Engineering).

For the purpose of future superconducting detector magnets and busbars for accelerator application, a development is on-going of **ReBCO-based Conductor-On-Round-Core Cable-In-Conduit (ReBCO-CORC-CIC)** conductors. This activity has already been on- going for some five years, and

a test of a prototype conductor in the SULTAN test facility at EPFL, location PSI, in a 12 T magnetic field back-ground and at variable temperature was foreseen.

Before shipping the conductor to EPFL/PSI for test at 4.3 K, the test of the conductor at 77 K (in liquid nitrogen) was necessary and without back-ground field, which involves running some 20 kA current through the sample, measuring the voltage taps on the conductor, and checking the sensors. *Dr. Ten Kate* with his team spent 24 h to perform these tests where the capacity to power up to 20 kA was the reason of his choice to use the TNA MagNet.

With a final goal to look for **axions dark matter employing custom-made microwave filters in magnetic dipole fields** Dr. Irastorza and his team, asked for equipment qualification for a detector at low temperature and high magnetic field. A strong magnetic field is necessary for axions convert into photons and then to be detected by a cavity. The higher the background magnetic field of the dipole magnet, the higher is the sensitivity of the experiment so the TNA offered to this experiment an 11T bore field model magnet. The team used the facility for 760 h and presented their results at the IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity

The TNA also organised a user workshop in FREIA (Sweden) with 45 participants and 35 talks in 2019. (<https://indico.uu.se/event/596/overview>).

5. List of Publications

TA Project Acronym	Publication Year	Authors	Title	References	Publication type	Peer reviewed	DOI	Open Access
ARIES-CERN-Magnet-2021-01	2021	J. Golm, S. Arguedas Cuendis, S. Calatroni, C. Cogollos, B. Döbrich, J.D. Gallego, J.M. García Barceló, X. Granados, J. Gutierrez, I.G. Irastorza, T. Koettig, N. Lamas, J. Liberadzka-Porret, C. Malbrunot, W. L. Millar, P. Navarro, C. Pereira Carlos, T. Puig, G. J. Rosaz, M. Siodlaczek, G. Telles, W. Wuensch	Thin Film (High Temperature) Superconducting Radiofrequency Cavities for the Search of Axion Dark Matter	IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity 2022	Journal publication	Yes	10.1109/TASC.2022.3147741	Yes